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HISTOPATHOLOGICAL AND RADIOLOGICAL ASPECT OF PROTECTIVE LUNG VENTILATION - EXPERIMENTAL MODEL

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Introduction The aim of this research was to indicate histopathological and radiological changes on experimental model, resulting from the application of protective mechanical ventilation on healthy and previously injured lungs.

Materials and Methods The research was conducted as a prospective experimental study, which included 10 experimental animals (pigs). Experimental animals were divided into two groups. In the control group (ventilation of healthy lungs) is applied CMV with low tidal volume (6-8 ml/kg) and PEEP 7 mbar. In the study group (before initiation of mechanical ventilation in the lungs through the tracheostomy cannula inserted gastric contents in the amount of 2 ml/kg body weight) was carried out the same type of mechanical ventilation, but with a gradual increase in PEEP from 7 to 15 mbar. Duration of mechanical ventilation of the lungs is limited to 240 min. Monitoring is included VT, Ppeak, Paw.mean, PEEP and X-ray of the lungs. Monitoring parameters were measured at intervals of 60 min. The second phase entailed taking samples of lung tissue of experimental animals at the end of the four-hour mechanical ventilation and send them to histopathological examination. Statistical analysis of the results were performed with Wilcoxon rank sum test ($p < 0.05$) and t-test of mean values ($p < 0.01$).

Results PEEP in both groups of experimental animals prevented the formation of significant edema of perivascular, interstitial and alveolar space, which was accompanied by the presence of small number of inflammatory cells. At the same time, PEEP was holding open the largest number of alveoli and small airways. Microatelectasis are weakly present in healthy lungs while not seen in injured lungs; rupture of alveolar septum was more prevalent in the study group. Rank sum test did not give statistical significance ($p > 0.05$). Subpleural cysts are visible on X-rays of the lungs of pigs from study group only after 240 min. of mechanical ventilation ($p < 0.05$). Student's t-test showed a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.01$) in mean values of Ppeak, Paw.mean and PEEP between the control and the study group.

Conclusion PEEP as an integral part of the protective lung ventilation keeps the alveoli and small airways open during the respiratory cycle with minimal expressed to totally absent histopathological and radiological changes in the parenchyma of healthy and previously injured lungs.

Welcome to Provence,

The **Summer Conference on Neonatology** has been planned to offer neonatologists and neonatal care professionals from all countries the unique combination of scientific excellence and the particular, relaxed atmosphere offered by Provence, during a few days at the beginning of the summer.

Given the success of the first conference, organized in 2013, with attendees from 48 countries, this second edition will offer an extended and updated programme, in the very same, typical setting of the historical Avignon.

The hottest knowledge in the areas of neonatal care which are particularly active today will be reviewed by a deliberately restricted panel of leading, world class experts, who have personally contributed to the current state of the art. They will also be given sufficient time to detail their own practice in the field, and address clinical cases.

Attendees of all levels of neonatal care will be welcome. However, to favour interactivity and personal exchanges, the number of registrations will be limited.

If you can't spend your summer in Provence, you can at least capture the flavours of its magic, in the outstanding venue of the Palace of the Popes in Avignon, in the country of lavender fields.

On behalf of the Faculty,

Umberto Simeoni, MD, NSQ

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